

inspire
SMART VILLAGE LABS

D6.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan - First

Q-PLAN

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Executive Summary

This document constitutes the first version of the INSPIRE project's Dissemination and Communication Plan (DCP).

INSPIRE aims to support the sustainable and inclusive development of European rural areas by promoting social well-being and inclusion of rural dwellers and groups in a vulnerable situation and enhancing governance frameworks in rural areas. In particular, the project contributes to advancing in a multi-dimensional way the concept of social inclusion in rural areas, and supports access to high-quality social services by rural citizens through a series of awareness-raising, capacity-building, and pilot deployment activities that focus on social entrepreneurship and improvement of social services in a set of 7 different pilot territories (e.g., coastal, rural, peri-urban, mountainous). To realise its objectives, the project provides a novel territorial typology of rural areas, sets up and operationalises 7 “Smart Village labs”, and enhances governance frameworks and informed policy-making through E-Democracy and user-innovation techniques, to eventually deliver a dedicated Rural Social Inclusion Policy Dashboard.

The document describes the overall communication activities and awareness-raising, dissemination of project results, management of all relevant activities, and partners’ responsibilities in this respect. It includes specific actions and activities that will be carried out by the INSPIRE consortium members in order to ensure success and maximum publicity for the project and its results. With that said, this deliverable outlines:

1. **What to disseminate** – Chapter two is devoted to the basic project-related information that will be conveyed throughout the project;
2. **To whom** – Chapter three consists of the key stakeholder groups that will serve as the main audiences for the project’s dissemination and communication activities;
3. **How** – Chapter four includes all the channels and tools that will be utilised by project partners in order to successfully implement the dissemination and communication activities;
4. **When** – Chapter five provides a time frame to ensure that the timing of the dissemination and communication activities is appropriate, during the lifespan of the project and beyond;
5. **Monitoring of the process** – Chapter six identifies the indicators to measure success in the dissemination and communication actions, enabling partners to refine efforts and actions over the course of the project.

The first version of the DCP defines the initial communication strategy that will be used throughout the years of the project and verifies that the INSPIRE website (Milestone 9) will be available by M6. The DCP will be updated in March 2026 (M18). There will also be a final deliverable “D6.4- Dissemination and communication results” available at the end of the project (M36). D6.4 will include the results and metrics of the dissemination and communication activities.

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Table of Terms and Definitions

Abbreviation	Definition
DCP	Dissemination and Communication Plan
D	Deliverable
EU	European Union
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
M	Month
NoI	Network of Interest
PAs	Practice Abstracts
SMA	Social Media Accounts
T	Task
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

1.1 Scope of the deliverable

This report, titled “D6.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan - First”, aims to design the strategy, plan and activities to be implemented under the INSPIRE project, with a view to maximising the project’s visibility and successfully convey its key messages and content to target audiences, identifying and employing the most suitable channels to spread them. Keeping that in mind, this deliverable outlines the approach to:

- (i) effectively communicate the project and disseminate its results,
- (ii) guide the partners in designing, planning and implementing their individual dissemination activities and
- (iii) continuously monitor the efficiency and the timely planning of the actions.

In this respect, the deliverable aims to:

- Describe the types of dissemination channels and tools to be utilised and the required actions and resources;
- Define responsibilities among partners;
- Summarise the internal monitoring, evaluating, and reporting of dissemination activities;
- Provide an indicative timetable/work planning of promotion activities during the project.

1.2 Structure of the deliverable

Taking the above into consideration, the “Dissemination and Communication Plan - First” is structured as follows:

- **Chapter 1 – Introduction:** Provides introductory information (scope, objectives, structure) with respect to the DCP
- **Chapter 2 – Dissemination assets:** Presents the main assets and information of the project during and beyond its span
- **Chapter 3 – Targeted stakeholder groups:** Presents the key stakeholder groups that will serve as the main audiences for the project’s dissemination and communication activities
- **Chapter 4 – Channels and tools:** Encompasses all the channels and tools that will be utilised for the project’s dissemination and communication activities, such as the project’s website, social media accounts (SMAs) etc.

- **Chapter 5 – Time plan:** Provides the timeframe for the communication and dissemination activities of the project partners
- **Chapter 6 – Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and monitoring:** Identifies the indicators to measure success in the dissemination and communication actions, enabling partners to refine efforts over the course of the project
- **Chapter 7 – Conclusions:** Pertains to the main decisions and aspects of the Dissemination and Communication Plan as well as the way forward

The Annexes include the dedicated forms for the dissemination and communication activities lists (guidelines, news reporting form, external events, synergies and “Dissemination and Communication reporting template”) to facilitate collaboration within WP6 and ensure useful resources for the project channels.

The methodology of INSPIRE for dissemination and communication builds on know-how, tools and templates that were developed internally by Q-PLAN as well as on good practices and templates from the literature. As in previous EU-funded projects, tailored modifications to the methodology were implemented for INSPIRE as well, in order to comply with the GA conditions and the particularities of the project. Along these lines, this deliverable presents the adjusted methodology as it was further developed and applied in the context of INSPIRE as well as presents the results from its application during the project.

2. Dissemination assets

The assets that follow will be disseminated by all partners with a view to maximising the project’s impact and visibility. This information will be conveyed in a meaningful way and well-tailored to each stakeholder group (these groups will be further described in Chapter 3).

- **Vision, objectives, strategic relevance, and key facts:** The vision, aim and strategic objectives of the project will be widely disseminated along with all the conceptual aspects of the project, namely the whole project concept and its innovative characteristics.
- **News, achievements, and results:** During the project, news, achievements, and results will be published through press releases, on the project’s website or partners’ websites to inform stakeholders about the project and its contribution to social inclusion in rural areas.
- **Events held by the project or in which partners will participate to present their results:** The events organised by the project and their results, will be widely disseminated to attract targeted stakeholder groups along with events in which partners are participating.
- **Key project results:** Key project assets, as depicted in the following Table 1, will be disseminated as widely as possible in order to stimulate the interest of prospective end-customers and nurture the ground for their post-project rollout.

Table 1. INSPIRE’s main assets/results¹

INSPIRE’s main assets/results
1. Social inclusion framework in rural areas
2. Quantitative datasets
3. Qualitative datasets
4. Repository of (social) services, initiatives and policies
5. Smart Village labs
6. Social economy solutions deployment roadmaps
7. MOOCs of European capacity-building programme
8. Network of Interest
9. Policy briefs
10. Guidebook and Toolkit
11. Territorial typology of EU rural areas
12. Services and Social Economy Atlas on Rural Empowerment;
13. Rural Social Inclusion Policy Dashboard

¹ These are the INSPIRE’s main assets/results as introduced in the DoA. They will be updated via activities foreseen in Task 6.3: Exploitation and sustainability.

3. Targeted stakeholder groups

The key stakeholder groups targeted via the dissemination and communication activities of INSPIRE are outlined in the following table:

Table 2 INSPIRE’s main target groups

Groups	
Groups in a vulnerable situation	Including migrants, minorities, elderly people, women (in vulnerable situations), people with disabilities, employees in the informal sector
Public sector	Including regional authorities, local authorities, public social service providers
Academia	Including universities, researchers, research centres
Private sector	Including social enterprises, local SMEs, capital investors, private service providers, universal designers, cooperatives
EU-wide stakeholders	Including EU policymakers, relevant DGs, EU-funded projects
Civil society	Including urban commuters, local NGOs
Other	General public, citizens, open platforms for sharing data and lessons learnt, etc.

4. Channels and Tools

INSPIRE uses a blend of online and offline communication channels and activities with a view to maximising the project’s visibility to its stakeholders. These channels and activities are presented in the list as follows:

- ✓ Graphical identity (logo, branded templates for reports and presentations)
- ✓ Promotional material (leaflet, poster/banner), videos, and newsletters
- ✓ Project website
- ✓ Project social media accounts on LinkedIn, Facebook, X and YouTube² and partner’s social media accounts
- ✓ Participation in external events and conferences
- ✓ INSPIRE’s events (workshops, webinars, and Final Conference)
- ✓ Synergies with relevant projects/initiatives
- ✓ Network of Interest activities
- ✓ Practice Abstracts

The dissemination and communication assets of the project will be distributed through the above-mentioned channels and tools to all targeted groups. This process will involve all the activities depicted in Figure 1. Q-PLAN has provided dedicated guidelines for the expected use of communication and dissemination channels to the consortium. These are listed in Annex I.

Figure 1: Dissemination and communication activities

² Other social media, such as Bluesky or Instagram might be added in the blend during the lifespan of the project.

The following table lists key channels for dissemination to be used throughout the course of the project.

Table 3. INSPIRE's dissemination main channels³

Channel	Description	Groups
Publications in scientific journals	The researchers of INSPIRE will disseminate the research results via scientific articles and conference presentations	academics and scientific community, policymakers and public authorities, relevant initiatives and networks
International/national conferences	The researchers of INSPIRE will disseminate the research results via conference presentations	policymakers, the academic and scientific community, relevant initiatives and networks, private sector actors
Workshops and networking events	Several events embedded in the design of INSPIRE (e.g., pilot warm-up events, EU-wide networking event, capacity building workshops, co-creation workshops, MOOCs programme) will address targeted groups of stakeholders, disseminating our results while also facilitating their exploitation.	groups in a vulnerable situation, business actors, policymakers, the academic community, relevant initiatives and networks, civil society, other
Communication activities	INSPIRE's communication activities (website, social media, synergies with other projects, events, etc.) will communicate and disseminate key project results	policymakers, academia, relevant initiatives, industry, and civil society, other

In addition, the following table summarises a preliminary set of the key messages addressed towards each targeted stakeholder group of INSPIRE as well as the set of dissemination and communication tools of the project used to convey them.

Table 4. Key messages and tools used for INSPIRE's targeted stakeholder groups

Target group	Tools and channels	Key messages
Groups in a vulnerable situation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Website, SMAs, workshops, MOOCs, Smart Village labs, Dissemination package Workshops and networking events, Communication activities 	INSPIRE increases social wellbeing by offering economic opportunities.
Public sector	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Website, SMAs, workshops, Nol, Guidebook, Smart Village labs, Atlas, Policy briefs, Dashboard 	INSPIRE upgrades governance framework for

³ Based on the DoA: "To ensure that dissemination channels are appropriately customised for ensuring reachability of results to various groups of people in a vulnerable situation, the updated version of the DCP will include more detailed information on additional dissemination channels that may be considered in each pilot case. These channels may include the deployment of alternative dissemination tools (e.g., local radio outlets, newspapers, post mails, tip-on cards, etc.) that will complement the overall dissemination strategy and toolkit and will effectively correspond to the unique profile and media landscape of each pilot ecosystem. In order to reach a wider pool of stakeholders, we will leverage our extensive networks."

Target group	Tools and channels	Key messages
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Publications in scientific journals, International/national conferences, Workshops and networking events, Communication activities 	social inclusion and economy in rural areas.
Academia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Website, SMAs, workshops, Nol, Guidebook, Atlas, Dashboard Publications in scientific journals, International/national conferences, Workshops and networking events, Communication activities 	INSPIRE provides knowledge on social economy and rural growth.
Private sector	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Website, SMAs, workshops, networking events, Nol, Guidebook, Atlas, Dashboard Publications in scientific journals, International/national conferences, Workshops and networking events, Communication activities 	INSPIRE enhances knowledge of social economy solutions and user innovation practices for rural development.
EU-wide stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Website, SMAs, workshops, Nol, Guidebook, Atlas, Dashboard Publications in scientific journals, International/national conferences, Workshops and networking events, Communication activities 	INSPIRE delivers policy solutions for social economy and social services in rural areas.
Civil society	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Website, SMAs, workshops, MOOCs, Networking events, Guidebook, Smart Village labs Workshops and networking events, Communication activities 	INSPIRE provides access to opportunities and augments social inclusion through enhanced social services.
Other	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Website, SMAs, workshops, MOOCs, Networking events, Guidebook, Smart Village labs Workshops and networking events, Communication activities 	

4.1 Graphical identity and promotional material

The design and creation of the project’s graphical identity (i.e. logo, templates, etc.) aim to ensure consistency in the project communication and promotional material throughout its duration. Promotional material will be mainly used at project workshops, webinars and external events where INSPIRE partners participate. It will be used, also, in the everyday publicity of the project. Moreover, press releases (on an ad hoc basis), newsletters (on a bi-annual basis), leaflets, posters and infographics will stress and demonstrate with evidence the benefits of INSPIRE, providing incentives for the involvement of different stakeholder groups in project activities, as well as foster their exploitation and uptake beyond the end of the grant.

Keeping that in mind, the main promotional material of the INSPIRE project is described in the following sub-sections.

Each partner will be responsible for translations (if considered necessary) and printing of the material according to its specific needs. Pilot partners specifically have a dedicated budget to print dissemination material to be distributed in their communities, so translations of the materials are considered essential in their cases, to be able to appeal to a wider audience. Partners should always consult and request approval from the Dissemination Manager/T6.1 Leader Q-PLAN before producing any kind of promotional material.

4.1.1 Project logo

The INSPIRE project logo was developed on the eve of the project (M2) to meet the visual and graphic requirements of the project. During the INSPIRE 1st monthly meeting, various logo options were presented to the project partners in order to allow them to express their preferences and select their favourite design. The chosen logo of INSPIRE was adopted in agreement with the absolute majority of partners and is presented in Figure 2 - Figure 5.

Figure 2: INSPIRE's project logo, version 1

Figure 3: INSPIRE's project logo, version 1 - tagline

Figure 4: INSPIRE's project logo, version 2

Figure 5: INSPIRE's project logo, version 2 - tagline

The project's logo is a combination mark which means that it is comprised of a combined wordmark and a distinctive pictorial/icon mark. The icon and text are integrated together to create an image.

The logo design for this project is primarily centred around a font-based approach, emphasising the project's acronym. Given the inherently memorable nature of the project's name, the strategic use of robust typography serves to enhance brand recognition significantly. The deliberate choice of a modern font aligns with the project's essence, effectively conveying its contemporary and forward-thinking attributes. This design approach underscores the project's commitment to creating a visually impactful and memorable brand identity.

The icon of the logo, as presented in Figure 6, encapsulates a circular shape, which consists of curved lines and 7 small circles symbolising the 7 Smart Village labs. The shapes created, remind the viewer of people coming together in a circle, depicting inclusive communities that are connected. The earthy colours are a reference to nature and rural areas (including peri-urban, coastal and mountainous areas), but they also refer to the inhabitants, inclusion and innovation.

Figure 6: INSPIRE logomark

The symbiotic integration of these elements in the icon contributes to a distinctive and meaningful visual representation of the project's mission.

The logo colours are used in all possible circumstances to ensure consistency and to reinforce the visual identity of INSPIRE. The chosen colour palette seamlessly integrates various shades of green, red, brown and purple. The main colours are two shades of green (#617570 & #829C94), two shades of red (#BF5C4D & #DE7A69), two shades of brown (#66402E & #A67857) and one shade of purple (#736675) linking inhabitants of rural areas (including peri-urban, coastal and mountainous areas) with inclusion and innovation. The colour palette used for the project is illustrated in Figure 7.

Figure 7: The colour palette of INSPIRE

In any communication material, deliverable, presentation, etc., produced within the scope of the INSPIRE project, the EU flag and funding acknowledgement, as depicted in Figure 8, must be prominently displayed.

Figure 8: The EU flag and funding acknowledgement

In compliance with the EU requirements on dissemination of results, as set in Grant Agreement number 101136592, Article 17, any dissemination of results (in any form, including electronic), must display the EU emblem with appropriate prominence and also include the following disclaimer:

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

4.1.2 Project leaflet, poster, and infographic

The project leaflet, poster and roll-up constitute an important pillar of communication activities and present essential project information (aim, objectives, partners, etc.). They will be created by January 2025 (M4). Apart from the general project leaflet, poster, and roll-up, promotional material to support INSPIRE events, infographics etc. will be prepared during the project, according to the needs of the responsible partners. This adaptive approach ensures responsiveness to the specific requirements articulated by individual partners, thereby enhancing the efficacy of communication initiatives associated with the project.

4.1.3 Templates

Templates have been created for the consortium partners in November 2024 (M2) (earlier than originally designed, which was for M4), to be able to produce their deliverables and presentations. Branded templates are designed to give slide presentations a consistent appearance and ensure uniformity. The branded templates enhance audience brand recognition and are memorable. INSPIRE's presentations include the logo, brand colours, fonts, and brand elements from the project's visual identity. In particular, templates for the project's deliverables and partners' presentations have been created and are available to project partners. In addition to the above templates, an INSPIRE letterhead has been developed, which is useful for various communication activities, such as invitations to events.

The following templates have been prepared for the INSPIRE project:

- INSPIRE presentation template;
- Project deliverables and reports template;
- Project letterhead.

The templates are shown below in Figure 9 - Figure 11:

Text box to insert the event title

PRESENTER: **Name Surname**
 LEAD BENEFICIARY: **Company Name**
 DDMM/YYYY | Venue

PARTNERS

Main Title Style

Main subtitle style

Main Title Style

Text template style

Text template style

28/11/2024 Footer

VISIT: www.inspire.eu
 CONTACT: info@inspire.eu

FOLLOW US:

PARTNERS

Figure 9: The presentation template

Dx.y Title

Beneficiary (Short Name)

DD/MM/YYYY

Figure 10: INSPIRE's deliverable template cover

Figure 11: INSPIRE's letterhead

4.1.4 Promotional video

A promotional video of approximately two (2) minutes will be produced in M12 to effectively reinforce the project's communication activities. The preparation of the video is the responsibility of Q-PLAN. The video will provide an overview of the project that includes vital information. The video is a great

way to highlight the mission and the vision of the project. It will be uploaded to INSPIRE's YouTube channel which will be set up as soon as the video is finalised.

4.2 INSPIRE's digital presence

4.2.1 INSPIRE's website

The project's official website will be accessible online by M6 (March 2025), catering to users on all devices without any limitations or restrictions. The website's URL will be established including the project's acronym, providing a centralised platform for information dissemination and engagement. Users will be able to access the portal seamlessly, fostering an inclusive and user-friendly experience.

For any inquiries or further information, we will encourage individuals to reach out to us via a designated contact email, which will be announced when the website is available.

It will constitute the main gateway to INSPIRE's activities, publications, news and events. Specifically, it will contain information about the project's concept and objectives, the consortium, the pilot areas, the relevant initiatives, as well as project news. Links to social media accounts of the project and to the project partner's web pages but also relevant initiatives and a dedicated section on the Network of Interest (NoI) will be included. In addition, it will be equipped with an online newsletter subscription for visitors/users. Finally, during the lifespan of the project, the website will also host the INSPIRE Policy Dashboard and its components, the websites of the Smart Village labs and the MOOCs of the training programme.

As the project evolves, the website will be further enriched with all public deliverables and promotional material. The news section of INPSIRE's website will be updated regularly, whenever an action/activity is taken. All partners are expected to contribute with news items. For this reason, a report form has been sent to the consortium in order to be filled out in detail with news. This form can be found in Annex II.

Site visits, statistics and other information on visitors' views (e.g., number of pages per visit, time on site, most viewed pages, etc.) will be measured using Google Analytics 4, to which the website will be registered since the first day of its operation.

Q-PLAN is responsible for the design, operation, and update of the project's website. The project website will be mentioned in all publicity material generated by the project consortium. At the end of the project, the website should reach 6,000 total visits. Taking

this into consideration, the website will be monitored periodically to assess whether the project is on the right path or if increased efforts are needed.

A dedicated report titled “**D6.3 INSPIRE Website**” will be elaborated by M6 by Q-PLAN, focusing on the website’s structure and content.

4.2.2 Social Media Accounts

In today’s society, the use of social media has become a necessary daily activity, therefore the project’s social media accounts (SMAs) are among the main pillars of promoting the project’s news, events and activities. INSPIRE utilises social media accounts on LinkedIn, Facebook, and X (YouTube is expected to be launched in M12). The above-mentioned accounts, except YouTube, have been launched in M3 (December 2024). If any needs arise, other social media may be used in the future (e.g., Bluesky, Instagram). Table 5 contains URL links to INPSIRE’s existing social media accounts.

Table 5. INSPIRE’s SMAs

Social media platform	Account name	URL
LinkedIn	INSPIRE project EU	https://www.linkedin.com/company/inspire-project-eu/
Facebook	Inspire project EU	https://www.facebook.com/profile.php?id=61569429994625
X (Twitter)	INSPIRE project	https://x.com/INSPIRE_EU1

The project’s social media will be continuously updated in English with news about the project’s activities and results, events, scientific news, and updates from several organisations/associations that promote social inclusion and innovation in rural areas, as well as news from related EU projects, etc. The frequency of social media posts will depend on the availability of news about the activities and results of the project.

In addition, hashtags are used on the project’s posts to help stakeholders easily find them and encourage interaction. The hashtags used on the project’s social media accounts are:

- #inspireproject
- #horizoneurope
- #socialinclusion
- #socialexclusion
- #innovation
- #socialentrepreneurship
- #ruralareas
- #smartvillagelabs

- #sustainability
- #wellbeing
- #empowerment
- #capacitybuilding
- #periurbanareas
- #coastalareas
- #mountainousareas
- #democraticengagement
- #civicparticipation
- #ruraldevelopment
- #vulnerablegroups
- #socialservices
- #socialeconomy
- #governanceframeworks
- #smartvillage
- #digitalinclusion

Q-PLAN is responsible for the administration of INSPIRE's social media accounts. All partners are requested to follow the social media accounts, disseminate the posts through their own networks, as well as to publish posts and news about the project regularly, through their organisations' social media.

4.2.2.1 LinkedIn

LinkedIn constitutes a significant networking tool for professionals, offers a more institutional approach and has therefore been selected as a core social media channel. The project's [LinkedIn page](#) was set up in M3 (December 2024) and it focuses on presenting the project, its objectives and results. All partners are responsible for timely updating and sharing their inputs to ensure their activities are duly promoted.

4.2.2.2 X

An [X \(Twitter\) account](#) was also launched in M3 (December 2024) aiming to build engagement with stakeholders and other European projects through the exchange of quick, frequent messages. X is known for communicating via short messages. That helps project stakeholders understand, quickly and easily what INSPIRE is and what it does. In addition, X can be used as a promotional tool for the project's events and workshops as it can create a buzz around the activity in a short period of time.

4.2.2.3 Facebook

A [Facebook account](#) was also created in M3 (December 2024) with the aim of building a strong community in various ways such as posting useful, relevant and interesting links. Facebook provides a fast, free connection to a significant number of stakeholders, so it gives the INSPIRE project an opportunity to share news and results. Like all INSPIRE social media accounts, the project’s Facebook page will be regularly updated either with posts related to the project or other related projects and initiatives.

Figure 12: INSPIRE’s SMA’s

4.2.2.4 YouTube

Finally, the INSPIRE YouTube channel will be established in M12, coinciding with the completion of the animated communication video outlined in section 4.1.4 (Promotional video). This channel is chosen to consolidate project videos in a singular, easily accessible location. The primary objective behind creating the YouTube channel is to disseminate promotional videos, leveraging the platform to expose the project to a broader audience.

4.2.3 Online newsletter and mailing list

An online newsletter will be prepared and distributed through Mailchimp, presenting among others the achieved results, upcoming activities and events, news from similar initiatives and news in the relevant scientific fields. The frequency of newsletter issues will depend on the amount and importance of news to be presented, with the target to produce a newsletter at least every 6 months, however, additional ad-hoc newsletters may be added if deemed necessary.

The initial recipients' list will be created and administered by Q-PLAN. The list will be continuously updated during the project, therefore everyone who is interested will be able to subscribe to the recipients' list by registering on the newsletter section of the project's website or unsubscribe according to GDPR rules. The recipients' list may also be used for the dissemination of other news and announcements related to the project activities.

The newsletter issues will be prepared by Q-PLAN, with the contribution of all partners regarding the content. The content of each issue will be decided and agreed upon among the consortium members. Partners are also required to disseminate the newsletter issues through their own channels and networks.

4.2.4 Press releases and other publications

During the project, at least five (5) scientific publications will be published in scientific journals/conferences. Publications in impactful peer-reviewed scientific journals is one of our key channels for dissemination. INSPIRE will disseminate the research and experimental results via scientific articles and conference presentations. The beneficiaries must ensure open access to peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to their results.

In addition, all authors are responsible for identifying any publishing opportunities and for carrying out all necessary actions to ensure publications of project news and results. Each partner will make an effort to produce publications in the highest quality, which not only reflects on the consortium's reputation but also on the INSPIRE project. All publications must cite or/and refer to the EU contribution and project grant agreement number, as required in Article 17 of Grant Agreement No. 101136592.

An indicative list of journals that can be used under the context of the project is given in the following table:

Table 6. Indicative Journals for dissemination of INSPIRE's results

Title	Impact factor	Title	Impact factor
Social Issues and Policy Review	9.857	Journal of Environmental Innovation and Societal Transition	5.7
Journal of Rural Studies	5.157	Review of Public Administration and Management	9.390
Regional Studies	4.672	Journal of Economic Perspectives	5.012
Sociologia Ruralis	3.2		

During M3 (December 2024), the INSPIRE project first press release was issued and generated by Q-PLAN. It communicated the INSPIRE kick-off meeting hosted at Mundo Matongé in Brussels, Belgium by WR on October 9th, 2024. The kick-off meeting saw all project partners converge to discuss their roles, responsibilities, and aspirations for the successful realisation of the project's specific objectives. The press release was shared with the consortium for further distribution.

The INSPIRE consortium, under the coordination of [White Research](#), consists of 18 partners across 11 countries: Belgium, the Netherlands, Spain, Greece, Czech Republic, Türkiye, Slovakia, Poland, France, Ireland and Romania. The consortium members include: [White Research](#) (WR), [University of Groningen](#) (RUG), [University of Barcelona](#) (UB), [South East European Research Centre](#) (SEERC), [Czech University of Life Sciences Prague](#) (CZU), [KOC University](#) (KOC), [Social Economy Europe](#) (SEE), [The European Association of Service providers for Persons with Disabilities](#) (EASPD), [European Social Women](#) (ENMW), [PEDAL Consulting](#) (PEDAL), [European A](#) (MedINA), [L'ADAPT](#) (L'ADAPT), [The Wheel](#) (WHEEL), [Q-PLAN](#), and [ARX NET](#) (ARX.NET).

December 16, 2024

PRESS RELEASE

INSPIRE: A new Horizon Europe project launched to promote social inclusion and inspire social entrepreneurs in European rural areas

INSPIRE project has officially kicked off. It is a project about inclusive governance and social services through social entrepreneurship in rural areas funded by the European Union, under Grant Agreement No. 101136592. With a nearly €5 million budget, this Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Action officially commenced in October 2024 and will last 36 months.

The project's Kick-off Meeting took place on October 9th, 2024, in Brussels, Belgium, and was organised by [White Research](#), the Project Coordinator. All partners gathered to discuss their roles, responsibilities, and aspirations for the successful realisation of the project's specific objectives, focusing on the first semester of the project. The pilot partners offered an overview of the key features of pilot locales, their main target groups and the potential of social economy regarding the provision of social services to rural inhabitants.

INSPIRE aims to promote social inclusion and enhance governance frameworks in European rural areas through a blend of novel research techniques, pilot interventions and policy solutions. It uses advanced methodologies and pilot actions and supports access to high-quality social services by rural citizens. The project will create an advanced territorial typology of rural areas in Europe, providing information about social inclusion drivers, status, risks, and trends.

It will also offer capacity-building on social entrepreneurship to rural entrepreneurs and encourage social entrepreneurship by vulnerable groups in a set of seven different pilot territories, through the concept of "Smart Village", with seven Smart Village Labs that will be created in Ireland, France, two in Greece, Poland, Slovakia and Romania that will serve as incubators of social entrepreneurship and social services, targeting groups in vulnerable situations.

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Views and opinions expressed are however not necessarily reflect those of the Research Executive Agency. Neither the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Figure 13: INSPIRE's 1st Press Release

4.3 INSPIRE events

4.3.1 Project events and workshops

The INSPIRE project is set to embark on a series of meticulously planned events, serving as powerful communication tools to disseminate information about the project's services and outcomes. These events, ranging from co-design workshops to capacity building for groups in a vulnerable situation, underscore the project's dedication to social inclusion in the pilot areas and will be organised to exchange knowledge and build capacity, disseminate results to the multi-actor policy network of interest, and present final achievements to stakeholders (Final Conference).

The project events and engagement activities are presented in the following list:

- **Smart Village Labs' workshops:** Focusing on the inclusion of the local community and groups in a vulnerable situation, the Smart Village Labs will deploy co-creation workshops, warm-up events, MOOCs and capacity-building workshops, user-innovation consultation workshops and local sustainability workshops.
- **Networking events and validation workshops:** Focusing on disseminating the project's results to interested stakeholders, as well as on validating the results, the project will deploy multiple networking and validation events. These events include the validation workshop, the EU-wide networking event, the pan-European virtual workshop with the Nol, and the project's Final Conference, where the final achievements of the project will be unveiled (M36), providing a comprehensive overview of the project's outcomes and advancements.
- **Interviews and surveys:** The project will employ multiple engagement activities such as interviews, focus groups, a Delphi exercise and surveys (national survey, paper-based surveys, CATI surveys) to make sure that the opinions of key stakeholders are taken into account in its research.

4.3.2 External events

Partners will participate in several external conferences and events of great interest to the project's target stakeholders to keep in touch with them, exchange knowledge, and communicate the project value propositions and results. In addition, the targeted events, both scientific and business, will relate to the knowledge fields of the project, the sectors it covers as well as the interests of the project's primary stakeholders. The goal is to keep in touch with the latest advances in research and industry across Europe, share knowledge with respective communities, and establish contacts and interactions with key stakeholders, while at the same time communicating the results of the project. External events in which partners will participate include, among others, business events, exhibitions, scientific events and conferences. Partners should follow the guidelines below:

- If a partner is presenting, the general project presentation should be used with any modifications necessary to this file, keeping the same template unless the event considers it mandatory to use the event's template;
- During the event, it is important to disseminate the project's promotional material (leaflets, posters, etc.);

- A number of photos must be taken;
- The partner is requested to update the Dissemination and Communication Manager about the participation in the event and to share the photos taken, not later than ten days after the event;
- All partners are requested to fill in the tab located in the 'Dissemination and Communication reporting' Excel concerning their participation in external events. Submission is required no later than three weeks after the event. The table can be found in Annex III.

In the table below, an indicative list of external events relevant to INSPIRE is provided.

Table 7. INSPIRE indicative events

Indicative events for the dissemination of the project’s outcomes	
(i) European Social Services Conference	(v) National Rural Networks Meetings
(ii) Social Good Week	(vi) Social Economy: the future of Europe
(iii) Rural Development Conference	(vii) European Week of Regions and Cities
(iv) European Day of Social Economy Enterprises	(viii) European Employment and Social Rights Forum

4.3.3 Final conference

By the end of the project, a closing event (EU-wide Final Conference in M36) will take place, organised under the lead of Q-PLAN. The aim of this conference is to attract interested stakeholders from the project’s target groups, to spread the word for INSPIRE’s accumulated knowledge and to present the project’s final results and achievements as well as to promote their uptake across Europe. INSPIRE partners should contribute to further disseminate the final event through their own networks.

4.4 Synergies with relevant projects/initiatives

Synergies aim to promote collaboration and knowledge exchange while also achieving more efficient and effective use of their resources. The INSPIRE project aims to establish synergies with key projects and initiatives, including the sister projects, projects funded under the topics HORIZON-CL2-2022-TRANSFORMATIONS-01-02 and HORIZON-CL2-2021-TRANSFORMATIONS-01-03, other active relevant Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe projects, and projects funded under other EU programmes.

Among the relevant projects that serve as a significant reference point for the INSPIRE project are initiatives such as:

- (i) MOBI-TWIN, which aims to address urban mobility challenges by fostering integrated mobility solutions and resilient infrastructure, focusing on sustainability and reducing urban congestion;

- (ii) ESSPIN, a project dedicated to the development of next-generation energy systems through the promotion of decentralized renewable energy networks and energy storage innovations that enhance grid stability and efficiency;
- (iii) EXIT project, which investigates transformative digital technologies, emphasizing the practical implementation of smart data systems and artificial intelligence for industry and public services modernization;
- (iv) PREMIUM-EU, which supports European innovation ecosystems by facilitating partnerships between research organizations, SMEs, and policy-makers, fostering a collaborative environment for groundbreaking innovations and sustainable economic development; etc.

ERDN with the support of all partners, will create communication pathways with those projects for collaboration, knowledge exchange, and joint activities.

Synergies will be decided after discussions with the relevant projects and initiatives' representatives and may involve joint communication and dissemination activities (such as press releases and campaigns, invitation of other projects to participate in our events or vice versa, organisation of joint webinars to present progress and results, etc.).

As part of the INSPIRE project's activities, a project identification form template was prepared by ERDN and submitted to project partners for review in .doc format. Simultaneously, a Google Forms survey is being developed. It will be made available to potential sister projects only after collecting feedback from project partners. Once the consultation process is completed, project partners will be asked to distribute the form among initiatives similar to INSPIRE, based on predefined collaboration criteria. After receiving submissions, ERDN will compile a summary of the survey results and present it to project partners for the joint selection of ≥ 10 most relevant projects for further collaboration.

Simultaneously, preliminary considerations are being made regarding a potential promotional strategy, including prospective joint information campaigns, participation in relevant events, and the organization of webinars to present project progress and results. Any future actions will be carefully evaluated and undertaken only after a thorough analysis of the survey data and consultations with project partners, ensuring alignment with mutual goals and project capabilities.

The INSPIRE project has committed to continuously seeking new collaboration opportunities, remaining open to initiatives from other projects to maximise mutual benefits. Collaboration with other projects and building a network of synergies is a key element of the INSPIRE strategy. These activities aim not only to enhance the effectiveness of project communication and dissemination but also to jointly create innovative solutions addressing the challenges of contemporary socio-economic transformations

All partners should keep in mind that the INSPIRE dissemination and communication strategy cannot reach its full potential unless meaningful collaboration with related projects is established. In this respect, the consortium should remain vigilant, actively seeking new collaborations and joint actions to ensure the project's success.

Results from clustering activities will be reported in **D6.4 Dissemination and communication results** (M36).

4.5 Network of Interest - NoI

As part of T5.1, ERDN is in charge of bringing together key stakeholders from several rural areas in Europe to set up an interactive multi-actor Network of Interest (NoI), which will include (i) policy makers, (ii) NGOs and vulnerable groups organisations, and (iii) social enterprises. The NoI will support social empowerment of groups in a vulnerable situation through the social economy, supporting at the same time the outreach of the INSPIRE project and the dissemination of its results. In order to reach a wider pool of stakeholders, partners will leverage their extensive network as indicated below:

Table 8. Consortium networks

Consortium networks for dissemination and exploitation results	
European Rural Development Network (ERDN)	Global Social Economy Forum (GSEF)
European Social Network (ESN)	European Smart Villages Forum (ESVF)
European Association of Service providers with Persons with Disabilities (EASPD)	Global Network for Entrepreneurs with Disabilities (GNED)

The multi-actor approach will not only facilitate the exchange of knowledge, best practices, and experiences, but also promote collective action that enhances social inclusion, equality, and sustainable economic development in rural areas. By uniting these diverse actors, the NoI will contribute to the strengthening of social cohesion within rural communities and to improving the resilience and adaptability of vulnerable groups in the face of socio-economic challenges.

The NoI will be structured to ensure that all relevant stakeholders, including marginalized communities and at-risk populations, have an active voice in shaping the development of social economy initiatives. In addition to fostering direct collaboration, the NoI will play a crucial role in the outreach and dissemination of the INSPIRE project’s results. By connecting with a broad spectrum of local, regional, and national stakeholders, the NoI will serve as a conduit for disseminating project findings, raising awareness, and advocating for policy change that benefits vulnerable groups and strengthens the role of the social economy.

To maximize the impact of this network, partners will leverage their extensive existing networks, drawing on relationships with local government authorities, community leaders, and sector-specific organizations across rural Europe. This will ensure that the NoI reaches a broad and diverse audience and facilitates cross-border learning and collaboration.

Furthermore, the project will ensure continuous engagement through digital platforms, enabling real-time collaboration and exchange of resources, while also incorporating feedback mechanisms that allow for adaptive learning throughout the project cycle. These activities will not only raise awareness of the INSPIRE project’s outcomes but will also help integrate innovative ideas and evidence-based practices into the wider policy and social economy landscapes.

Through this approach, the **Network of Interest** will become a cornerstone of both the **INSPIRE project** and ongoing efforts to build resilient, inclusive, and sustainable rural communities across Europe.

Results from the activities regarding the Nol will be reported in **D5.1 INSPIRE policy recommendations** (M32).

4.6 Practice Abstracts

INSPIRE will also elaborate two deliverables that contain the project’s Practice Abstracts (PAs) in the framework of enhancing the dissemination and policy uptake of the INSPIRE key results. The PAs will be produced under T6.1 to facilitate the flow of information from INSPIRE to end-users and share relevant innovative and practice-oriented knowledge. The PAs will be prepared by UB, ESN, WR, SEERC, PEDAL and WHEEL, each partner responsible for their respective asset, using guidance and templates elaborated by ERDN based on the EIP-AGRI common format (with the assistance of all partners, especially SEERC). More specifically, as also seen in Table 9:

- Deliverable **D6.7 – Practice Abstracts – batch 1** will contain 2 practice abstracts: (i) Territorial typology of EU rural areas (prepared by UB) and (ii) the Services and Social Economy Atlas on Rural Empowerment (prepared by ESN).
- Deliverable **D6.8 – Practice Abstracts – batch 2** will contain 4 practice abstracts: (i) Smart Village labs (prepared by WR); (ii) the Rural Social Inclusion Policy Dashboard (prepared by SEERC); (iii) the Social economy solutions deployment roadmaps (prepared by PEDAL); and the (iv) Portfolio of INSPIRE innovative solutions (prepared by WHEEL).

Table 9: INSPIRE’s Practice Abstracts

#	Lead partner	PAs included	Responsible partner	Deliverable	Time
Practice Abstracts – batch 1	ERDN	Territorial typology of EU rural areas	UB	D6.7	M18
		Services and Social Economy Atlas on Rural Empowerment	ESN		
Practice Abstracts – batch 2	ERDN	Smart Village labs	WR	D6.8	M36
		Rural Social Inclusion Policy Dashboard	SEERC		
		Social economy solutions deployment roadmaps	PEDAL		
		Portfolio of INSPIRE innovative solutions	WHEEL		

4.7 Dissemination channels

A tentative list of EU dissemination channels that may be utilised by INSPIRE throughout its duration is provided below:

- **CORDIS** is the EC primary source of results from projects funded by the EU's framework programmes for R&I.
- The **Horizon Results Booster** addresses projects eager to go beyond their dissemination and exploitation obligations under Horizon funding schemes.
- **Horizon Results** is a repository of Key Exploitable Results of EU-funded research and innovation projects.
- **Open Research Europe** is an open-access publishing platform that beneficiaries can use to publish any research results coming from R&I funded programmes, and it is in line with the EU's open science policy.
- **Horizon Dashboard** is an interactive knowledge platform where statistics and data on EU Research and Innovation programmes can be extracted.
- **Eurofound**. The European Foundation for the Improvement of Living and Working Conditions is a European Union Agency, whose role is to assist in the development of better social, employment and work-related policies.
- **The Horizon Magazine** is a publication by the European Commission that highlights cutting-edge European research and innovation, showcasing how EU-funded projects tackle global challenges and advance scientific progress.
- **EU-FarmBook** is a Horizon Europe project working at regional, national, and European level, to build an Online Platform, that offers a collection of vetted best practices for farmers and foresters, offered by Horizon research projects.
- **EU Info-days, workshops and conferences**

5. Timeline and implementation plan

In Figure 14, an indicative timeline and action plan of INSPIRE’s dissemination and communication activities is presented, spanning the whole duration of the project. The action plan will be adjusted accordingly as INSPIRE activities unfold to match the needs of the project.

Activity	Responsible Partner	Related WP	2024		2025						2026				2027																							
			1st year												2nd year				3rd year																			
			M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12	M13	M14	M15	M18	M16	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24	M25	M26	M27	M30	M28	M29	M31	M32	M33	M34	M35	M36	
Development of promotional material																																						
Logo	Q-PLAN	WP6																																				
Templates (report, presentation and letterhead)		All WPs																																				
Leaflet, poster, and infographic		WP6																																				
Promotional video		WP6																																				
Website																																						
Development and operation of project’s website	Q-PLAN	WP6																																				
Publicity through project’s website	All partners	All WPs																																				
Publicity through partners’ website	All partners	All WPs																																				
Social media networks																																						
Creation of social media accounts (Facebook, X, Youtube and LinkedIn)	Q-PLAN	WP6																																				
Publicity through projects’ social media	All partners	All WPs																																				
Publicity through partners’ social media	All partners	All WPs																																				
Publicity through project YouTube channel	Q-PLAN	WP6																																				
Digital presence																																						
Recipients list creation and update	Q-PLAN	WP6																																				
E-newsletter	Q-PLAN	WP6																																				
Publications																																						
Non – scientific (press releases)	All partners	WP6																																				
Scientific publications and conference papers	All partners	WP6																																				
External events																																						
Exhibitions, business events, information days etc.	All partners	WP6																																				
Scientific events, conferences etc.	All partners	WP6																																				
Project workshops																																						
Trainings, workshops and webinars	All partners	All WPs																																				
Final Conference																																						
EU-wide Final Conference	Q-PLAN	All WPs																																				
Synergies with related projects/initiatives																																						
Synergies with related projects/initiatives	ERDN, all partners	WP6																																				
Network of interest (NoI)																																						
Network of Interest (NoI)	ERDN, all partners	WP6																																				
EU dissemination channels																																						
CORDIS , Horizon Results Booster , Horizon Results, Open Research Europe , Horizon Dashboard , Eurofound,Horizon Magazine, EU-FarmBook EU Info-days, workshops and conferences	Q-PLAN	WP6																																				

Figure 14: INSPIRE’s timeline

6. Key Performance Indicators and monitoring

To measure the success of INSPIRE’s dissemination and communication strategy, the following KPIs will be employed, and all dissemination activities will be monitored with their results being compared to the KPIs so as to assess whether INSPIRE is on the right path or if increased efforts need to take place.

Table 10: INSPIRE’s dissemination KPIs

Indicator	Interim target (M18)	Target (impact)
Total visits to the project’s website	≥ 2,000	≥ 6,000
Followers on social media accounts	≥ 200	≥ 500
Number of newsletters	3	6
Number of newsletter subscribers	≥ 100	≥ 200
Number of publications in journals	≥ 2	≥ 5
Participation in external events	≥ 3	≥ 10
Synergies with other initiatives	≥ 5	≥ 10
Network of Interest participants	≥ 30	≥ 60
Participants in Final Conference	N/A	≥ 75
Promotional video total views	≥ 200	≥ 500
Participants in EU-wide networking event	-	≥ 40

To meet target values, project partners are expected to continuously carry out publicity actions and also report all publicity and communication outcomes regularly. Q-PLAN will be overall responsible for monitoring and evaluating the INSPIRE dissemination activities.

Partners are required to provide detailed reports on all communication and dissemination actions through the INSPIRE “Dissemination and Communication Reporting Excel”, which is sent to all partners via email. The table can be found in Annex V. Q-PLAN will notify all partners in advance for input collection.

Any promotional material related to the project produced by a partner should be reviewed and approved by the WP6 leader, Q-PLAN. Each project partner should promptly contact Q-PLAN if they identify opportunities, problems, or risks during the planning or implementation of publicity actions.

7. Conclusions

This document, titled “Dissemination and Communication Plan - First”, provides the dissemination and communication strategy, tools, framework and guidelines for the successful implementation of dissemination and communication activities throughout the lifespan of the project and beyond. As the project evolves, this document will be updated and refined in order to provide a more detailed analysis of the dissemination actions and plans. The actions and plans of this deliverable answer to the following questions:

- What to disseminate?
- To whom?
- How?
- When?

This document also provides the monitoring mechanism of the dissemination activities, which is based on targeted KPIs. By communicating the project’s tangible and intangible assets through the most effective channels and tools to timely reach the targeted groups, INSPIRE will be able to not only go beyond these ambitious KPIs but most importantly lay the foundations for the successful rollout, replication and thus sustainability of its outcomes. As the project evolves, the DCP will be updated and progress against targets will be measured in March 2026 (M18). Results will be presented and progress against targets will be measured in “D6.4-Dissemination and communication results” (M36).

8. Annexes

8.1 Annex I – INSPIRE’s D&C Guidelines

8.2 Annex II – News reporting form

GA 101136592

1. News

Picture(s)	
Title	
News (main content)	<p>Please <u>insert here</u> the content in a <u>narrative way</u>, while trying to provide answers to the following questions (if applicable):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Who was or will be the organisation(s) responsible for organising the activity or developing the solution / Who was or will it be for (target group or groups if applicable) • When did or will it take place or is / will be available (if applicable) • Where did or will it take place or is / will be available (if applicable) • Why is this activity important / Why did or will we need participation or contribution (if applicable) • How was or will it be implemented (very briefly) • What were or will be the main benefits or outcomes / results / conclusions
Key words/ hashtags (for social media)	

2. Attachments

Please attach any relevant pictures/ images as separate .png or .jpg files with as high resolution as possible.

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8.3 Annex III – External attended events (dissemination and communication reporting sheet)

Events										
#	Event's Name	Thematic Focus	Date	Location	Registration fees	Specific requirements for participation (e.g. abstract submission etc)	Deadline for abstract submission (if applicable)	Website	Added by (Partner)	Status
1										
2										
3										Cancelled
										Ongoing
										Done

8.4 Annex IV – Synergies Survey

INSPIRE: Survey on Rural Development, Social Inclusion, and Entrepreneurship Initiatives

Dear Participant,

We kindly invite you to take part in a survey designed to gather valuable insights into projects addressing the development of rural areas, social inclusion, and entrepreneurship. Your input will help us better understand the scope, impact, and innovative approaches of various initiatives across regions.

This survey is structured to cover key aspects of your project, including:

- Basic project details and thematic focus
- Strategies for social inclusion and tackling exclusion
- Support for social entrepreneurship and human capital development
- Collaboration efforts and joint actions
- Evaluation methods and impact assessment

The information you provide will contribute to identifying best practices, challenges, and opportunities in rural development initiatives. It will also help foster cross-sector collaboration and strengthen partnerships on a regional, national, and European scale.

Who should complete this survey? This questionnaire is intended for project coordinators, team members, or other stakeholders actively involved in the planning or implementation of projects related to rural development, social entrepreneurship, or inclusion.

Estimated completion time: Approximately 10–15 minutes.

Your responses will remain confidential and will only be used for the purposes of analysis and reporting in the context of this initiative.

We greatly appreciate your time and contribution to advancing sustainable and inclusive development!

Basic Information About the Project

This section collects key details about your project, including its name, funding source, and thematic focus. It helps us understand the project's scope and primary objectives.

Project Name *

Twoja odpowiedź _____

Acronym *

Twoja odpowiedź _____

Grant Agreement Number (for EU-funded projects)

Twoja odpowiedź _____

Funding Source (for projects not funded by Horizon Europe)

Twoja odpowiedź _____

Contact Person *

Twoja odpowiedź _____

Does your project address the development of rural areas? *

Yes

No

What is the main thematic area of your project? *

Social inclusion in rural areas

Social entrepreneurship

Public and social services

Environmental protection

Infrastructure development

Digital transformation

What is the scale of the project's impact? *

Local

Regional

National

European

	A	B	C	D
1	Sygnatura czasowa			
2	Project Name			
3	Acronym			
4	Grant Agreement Number (for EU-funded projects)			
5	Funding Source (for projects not funded by Horizon Europe)			
6	Contact Person			
7	Contact Person's Email Address			
8	Does your project address the development of rural areas?			
9	What is the main thematic area of your project?			
10	What is the scale of the project's impact?			
11	What indicators are used to measure social inclusion in your project? (multiple answers possible)			
12	Does the project define or explore the concept of social exclusion in rural areas?			
13	What are the main social groups benefiting from your project? (multiple answers possible)			
14	Does your project identify specific needs or challenges for vulnerable groups in rural areas?			
15	Does your project plan long-term actions to support vulnerable groups in rural areas?			
16	Does the project support the development of social entrepreneurship in rural areas?			
17	What forms of support does your project provide for social entrepreneurship? (multiple answers possible)			
18	Does the project involve the local community in decision-making and the development of social initiatives?			
19	Does your project include actions to support the development of human capital in rural areas?			
20	Does your project contribute in any way to improving sustainable mobility in rural areas?			
21	Does your project address issues related to migration or youth mobility?			
22	What actions are being undertaken in the project to support cross-sectoral collaboration? (e.g., between public, private, and social sectors; multiple answers possible)			
23	Does the project plan to establish partnerships with other initiatives at the regional or national level?			
24	What social impact assessment tools are used in your project? (multiple answers possible)			
25	Does the project include educational, training, or capacity-building programs for local communities?			
26	Can your project collaborate with other initiatives at the European level to strengthen rural development?			
27				
28				
29				
30				
31				
32				
33				

< > Liczba odpowiedzi 1 +

Gotowy Ułatwienia dostępu: zbadaj

8.5.3 Publications

Last Updated		DD/MM/YYYY								
#	Type of PID	Type of publication	Title of the scientific publication	Authors	Title of the journal or equivalent	Number	ISSN or eISSN	Publisher	Month of publication	Year of publication
1										
2	DOI									
3	Handle	select the list								
	ARK									
	URI									
	pURL									
	Other									
	None									
		Article in journal								
		Publication in conference proceeding/ workshop								
		Books/ monographs								
		Chapters in books								
		Thesis/ dissertation								
		Other								

Month of publication	Year of publication	Was the publication available in open access through the repository at the time of publication	Peer-reviewed	PID (Publisher version of record)	Book Title	Did you charge OA publishing fees to the project?	Type of publishing venue	Article processing costs that will be charged to the project
		Yes					Hybrid venue	
		No					Full open access venue	
							Full subscription venue	
			Yes					
			No					
								Yes
								No

Communication activities
Dissemination activities
Publications
Events
+

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